

Correction

Correction: Russo, B., et al. Assessment of Urban Flood Resilience in Barcelona for Current and Future Scenarios. The RESCCUE Project. *Sustainability* 2020, 12, 5638

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The authors would like to make the following corrections about the published paper [1]. The changes are as follows:

Replacing Table 5.

Table 5. Potential pluvial flood impacts due to climate change assessed by loosely coupled models. EAD: expected annual damage.

Model	Type of Impact	Indicator (BAU vs. Baseline)	Values for T/EAD
1D/2D USM	Intangible	Increase (%) of high flood risk area for pedestrian and vehicles	Pedestrians: +30 (T10), +34 (T50), +32 (T100), +30 (T500) Vehicles: +38 (T10), +42 (T50), +34 (T100), +25 (T500)
1D/2D USM + Damage model	Tangible	Increase (%) of EAD (including properties, vehicles and indirect damages)	42%

Table 5. Cont.

Model	Type of Impact	Indicator (BAU vs. Baseline)	Values for T/EAD
1D/2D USM + Traffic model	Tangible & Intangible	Increase (%) of km of closed roads; EAD due to travelling time rise	+31 (T10), +60 (T50), +66 (T100), +116 (T500); + 0.18 M€
1D/2D USM + Electric model	Tangible & Intangible	Increase (%) of the number of flooded electric infrastructures; related EAD	+31 (T10), +60 (T50), +66 (T100), +116 (T500); + 0.18 M€
1D/2D USM + Waste model	Intangible	Increase (%) of the number of unstable waste containers	+13 (T10), +12 (T50), +11 (T100), +10 (T500); 0.012M€

With:

Table 5. Potential pluvial flood impacts due to climate change assessed by loosely coupled models.

Model	Type of Impact	Indicator (BAU vs. Baseline)	Values for T/EAD
1D/2D USM	Intangible	Increase (%) of high flood risk area for pedestrian and vehicles	<u>Pedestrians:</u> +30 (T10), +34 (T50), +32 (T100), +30 (T500) <u>Vehicles:</u> +38 (T10), +42 (T50), +34 (T100), +25 (T500)
1D/2D USM + Damage model	Tangible	Increase (%) of EAD (including properties, vehicles and indirect damages)	+42%
1D/2D USM + Traffic model	Tangible and Intangible	Increase (%) of km of closed roads; EAD due to travelling time rise	+31 (T10), +60 (T50), +66 (T100), +116 (T500); +0.18 M€
1D/2D USM + Electric model	Tangible and Intangible	Increase (%) of the number of flooded electric infrastructures; related EAD	+13 (T10), +12 (T50), +11 (T100), +10 (T500); +0.12M€
1D/2D USM + Waste model	Intangible	Increase (%) of the number of unstable waste containers	<u>Empty:</u> +27 (T10), +28 (T50) <u>50% full:</u> +28 (T10), +32 (T50) <u>100% full:</u> +28 (T10), +36 (T50)

Reference

- Russo, B.; Velasco, M.; Locatelli, L.; Sunyer, D.; Yubero, D.; Monjo, R.; Martínez-Gomariz, E.; Forero-Ortiz, E.; Sánchez-Muñoz, D.; Evans, B.; et al. Assessment of Urban Flood Resilience in Barcelona for Current and Future Scenarios. The RESCCUE Project. *Sustainability* **2020**, *12*, 5638. [[CrossRef](#)]

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